

REVISITING SERVICE DOMINANT LOGIC: A CONTEMPORARY PERSPECTIVE ON VALUE CO-CREATION

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Abstract

Purpose – To investigate the concept of Service-Dominant Logic within a value co-creation framework. From this point of view, a representation on how S-D Logic redefines the co-creation process will be provided, along with the roles of actors engaged into the process of value co-creation.

Methodology/approach - This paper aims to explore and highlight the relevant definitions, existing frameworks, theories and models by using qualitative research methodology. From this point of view, a systematic literature review regarding existing papers on Service-Dominant Logic and value co-creation processes has been performed.

Findings – Through this literature review, in this paper we identify key themes and patterns which emphasize the use of Service-Dominant Logic principles and its relevance for the current research stream.

Research limitations/implications – The main limitation of this research is related to the fact that in order to understand Service-Dominant Logic, the methodological approach was based only on secondary data from the existing literature. While the qualitative approach provides a comprehensive understanding of the analyzed concepts, it also requires the need of filling the gap in terms of quantitative validation by using primary data.

Practical implications – From the practical point of view, implementation of the Service-Dominant logic within various industries has been highlighted. Customers engagement, enhancing innovation activities or processes and service delivery represent few of the most important practical implications strengthened by S-D Logic implementation. From this perspective, practical and existing examples have been provided, such as innovative marketing strategies, user involvement into content generation within music industry platforms, healthcare collaborative patterns.

Originality/value – This article contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing systematic literature review in order to highlight practical applications of the S-D Logic and to emphasize its relevance for the value co-creation field of research.

Key words: *service, co-creation, value, service-dominant logic.*

Introduction

The landscape of marketing faced significant transformation over the past few decades and one of the main reasons for this is marked by the rapid evolution of customer needs and technological advancements. For a long time, marketing focused on the exchange of goods with businesses trying all kinds of modalities to sell their products to customers, but this product-centric view has been gradually replaced by a distinctive approach that focuses on delivering solutions to consumer problems. Moreover, it must be highlighted that in this evolving paradigm, the concept of co-creation has become more and more popular.

Co-creation is a process that involves a collaborative partnership between businesses and consumers in the process of value creation. The key aspect within this process is related to the creation of collaborative interactions among both parties. According to De Koning et al those type of collaborative linkages are no longer related only to the created transactions, they are rather concentrated on the experience generation (De Koning et al., 2016). More precisely, as Prahalad and Ramaswamy (2004) mention, co-creation is used in the context of defining a new category of “*informed, connected, empowered, and active*” consumers. Therefore, apart from generating new innovations, this co-creative process ensures that the solutions provided are better aligned with the real needs of the users.

Parallel to the rise of co-creation is the growing recognition that the customers at the core of this type of process are seeking to gain potential solutions, rather than just stand-alone products. With this type of transition becoming more and more popular, it eventually led to the emergence of what we know today as the Service-Dominant Logic.

Service-Dominant Logic, a paradigm that was originally presented by Vargo and Lusch, offers a different research paradigm on the concept of value and value generation (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). The authors' approach is bringing forward the importance of established interactions among different actors (Vargo and Lusch, 2004; Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004).

From this point of view, the main objective of the present research is to explore the S-D Logic landscape in order to highlight the meaning of created value, the most relevant patterns and frameworks of analysis.

The Shift from Goods to Service

In order to understand the value creation, process it is relevant to highlight the transition from the logic dominated by goods manufacturing to the approach where services are dominant within economical exchanges (Vargo et al., 2020). In G-D Logic, the focus is concentrated on tangible goods and the value embedded in these goods by producers. In contrast, S-D Logic considers that the offered services are the ones relevant as the basis for economic exchange. This approach brings forward the development and use of generated knowledge, skills and competences beneficial for various actors, aspects that Vargo and Lusch (2004) use in redefining service as “*the application of specialized competences (knowledge and skills) through deeds, processes, and performances for the benefit of another entity or the entity itself*”.

This shift requires recognizing that goods are merely vehicles for service delivery and that value is co-created in fact through interactions between providers and beneficiaries, highlighting the intangible, dynamic nature of value creation, where the focus shifts from static products to continuous and collaborative processes (Vargo and Lusch 2004; 2006).

Operant and Operand Resources: Understanding their roles in S-D Logic

Resources are the essence of any service-oriented organization, supporting all aspects of their operations and initiatives and therefore it is absolutely imperative that they are managed and used properly, encouraging innovation and sustaining competitive advantage in a dynamic environment.

In the same context of highlighting the importance of resources, Storbacka et al. (2012) argue that they are crucial components of design because they build the foundation for co-creation. One relevant remark would be that resources can be seen as enablers and barriers simultaneously, as their presence can motivate other actors to engage in co-creation activities, while their absence can even make co-creation impossible (Storbacka et al., 2012).

Vargo and Lusch (2004) distinguish between two types of resources: operand and operant. "Operand resources" (Vargo and Lusch, 2004, pp 2) are typically tangible and static, such as raw materials and physical goods (Arnould et al., 2006; Vargo and Lusch, 2004). These resources are those that consumers have the ability to allocate for achieving specific operations, including social and life projects and it is important to mention that these consumers possess a collection of material objects that vary in quantity and quality, some of which are acquired through exchanges with merchants, while others include gifts, inherited items, found objects, or self-created items (Arnould et al., 2006).

In contrast, operant resources are intangible and dynamic, encompassing skills, knowledge, and competences that act upon operand resources in value creation process. This type of resources is considered as the most important of value creation and achieving the competitive advantage (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). Moreover, the operant resources are perceived through the lens of companies' intangible capabilities, skills and knowledge which are required and enabled in order to respond to the customers' needs and contexts (Vargo and Lusch, 2004). Vargo and Lusch (2004; 2008) also emphasized that these resources are dynamic and in continuous development.

Vargo and Lusch (2004, 2006, 2008) view operant resources as essential in the service-centered logic. They highlight that abundant natural resources are leveraged through innovation and knowledge, providing the example of the microprocessor (primarily composed of silicon, which is just a common resource, but which requires additional leverage in order to be valuable). Therefore, resources are not just raw materials and they become valuable tools when enhanced with human intelligence: "*resources are not, they become.*" (Vargo and Lusch, 2004).

Arnould et al. (2006) state that the relationship between firms and customers can be understood through the lens of operant resources, emphasizing the active role both parties play in the value creation process. From the firms' perspective, customers are seen as operant resources - active participants who add value through how they use and integrate products and services into their lives, while in a similar manner, from the customers' viewpoint, firms become essential operant resources, providing the tools necessary to achieve personal goals and improve quality of life (Arnould et al., 2006).

Core principles and fundamental laws of S-D Logic

The principles underlying Service-Dominant Logic were originally formulated into fundamental premises. Vargo and Lusch originally presented the eight relevant principles of S-D logic in their 2004 article but since then, these principles have gone through several transformations, with additional premises being added as S-D logic has been expanded and elaborated (Vargo and Lusch, 2006, 2008, 2016). Currently, S-D logic consists of eleven foundational premises with five of these identified as the fundamental laws of S-D logic (Vargo and Lusch, 2016). This

approach can be seen as a relevant keystone for other principles generation. In this research paper, our focus was on highlighting and summarizing these fundamental laws of Service-Dominant Logic as it is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Service – Dominant Logic Fundamental Laws (Vargo and Lusch, 2016)

No.	Fundamental Laws	Description
FL1	<i>Service is the core resource for exchange</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defined through created competences • Service is the core of existing exchanges among actors • Products are serving as a resource for service
FL2	<i>Value is co-created by multiple actors</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value co-creation is main process • Co-creation means interactions and relations among different actors • Interactions materialized through resources allocation and exchange • Customer plays a central role in value creation
FL3	<i>Actors within an ecosystem act as resource integrators</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple sources for necessary resources • Use complex networks of potential actors' engagement • Co-creation through complex interactions • Service ecosystem at the core
FL4	<i>Value is always defined by the users</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating value based on the context • Relies on customers experience and the manner of usage • How and when the customer is engaging into co-creative process
FL5	<i>Value co-creation is coordinated through actor-generated institutions and institutional arrangements:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There should exist an orchestrator • Coordination can be realized by using specially designed rules and norms • Collaborative interactions depend on the environment they are evolving

The meaning of “value” in S-D Logic

Vargo et al. (2020) highlighted that collaborative exchange of value represents the core of the entire logic. The authors explored the idea that in value co-creation the provided services can be seen as delivery channels (Vargo, et. Al, 2020). However, in this case, intangible resources are highly valued, such as competences, skills and knowledge (Vargo, et. Al, 2020) and relations and interactions are viewed rather as dynamic and mutually beneficial exchange. This type of approach eventually led to different meanings of value.

In the Goods-Dominant (G-D) logic, the concept of “value in exchange” is preferred as it suggests the meaning of created and embedded value by and within the existing products or goods by the manufacturer itself (Grönroos, 2008). Alternatively, Grönroos (2008) suggests that value is actually generated and created by the beneficiary only when it is consumed, naming it “value in use”.

Based on previous research, Grönroos explores the concept of value and its creation within the Service-Dominant Logic (Grönroos, 2008, 2011), concentrating his research on the exploration of distinguishing value in use and value in exchange, to highlight the role of value generators (clients) and value creators (manufacturers) and of the process itself (Grönroos, 2008).

According to Grönroos (2008), value in exchange is traditionally associated with the moment of exchange or transaction, where value is embedded in the product and realized through the exchange of goods and services for a specific price. This represents the classic view of economics and marketing which relies on transactional value. However, Grönroos (2008) emphasizes the second type of value, value in use, which refers to the value created and perceived by the customer in the context of the actual use or consumption of a product or service. Value in use highlights the importance of the customer experience and the personal processes by which the customer integrates the firm's resources into their daily activities, creating individual value. Consequently, the shift in value meaning can be traced, as it is represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The transition of the value concept from Goods-Dominant to Service-Dominant logic (Vargo and Lusch, 2004; Grönroos, 2008, 2011).

Therefore, Grönroos (2008, 2011, 2013) argues that firms do not directly "create" value and that instead, they facilitate value creation, with real value being generated by customers at the moment and in the context of use. Grönroos (2013) encourages firms to focus on understanding and enhancing value in use through customer interaction and by facilitating their value creation processes. This approach promotes a more customer-oriented perspective, contrasting with traditional product or transaction-oriented models.

Conclusion

Service-Dominant Logic represents a paradigm shift in understanding economic exchanges and value creation. Value co-creation, presented through the lens of dynamic resource allocation and exchange and by taking into account various actors and the relations established among them, can be seen as a complex framework to foster and promote innovation and service as a valuable resource. Based on this assumption, it can be noticed that the Service-Dominant Logic approach is rather focused on multiple actors' involvement, where resources are mainly intangible and an active engagement into the process is preferred.

As businesses and industries continue to evolve or even transform, the principles of this logic will become more and more relevant. By adopting a service-dominant perspective, organizations can better navigate the complexities of modern markets and enhance their competitive advantage, creating more sustainable and meaningful value for all of the stakeholders.

Service-Dominant Logic, while influential, cannot avoid criticism and faces challenges in its application and theoretical development. Campbell et al. (2013) argue that the S-D logic provides a narrow perspective on the economy and society by excessively focusing on operand resources (human capabilities) while neglecting the importance of operand resources (physical assets), underlining the fact that this logic underestimates the complexity of resources.

In conclusion, while Service-Dominant Logic has significantly shaped contemporary understanding of value creation and customer relationships, its future research should address its critics' concerns and evolve towards a more balanced perspective, aiming to refine S-D Logic by incorporating a more comprehensive view of resources and their interactions, ensuring its relevance and applicability across various economic and social contexts.

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